

Prevalence & Molecular Characterization Of Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamases In *Enterobacteriaceae*

Hassan Gulab¹, Fatima Zafar^{*2}, Attiya Shahzadi³, Fatima Tariq⁴, Usman Wajid⁵, Abbas Shahid⁶

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords

ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli*, Antimicrobial resistance (AMR), blaCTX-M, blaTEM, blaSHV genes, Antibiotic susceptibility testing, 16S rRNA phylogenetic analysis

Hassan Gulab¹

Department of Biological Sciences, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan.

Fatima Zafar^{*2}

Faculty of Sciences & Technology, Department of Microbiology, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.
*2mughalfatima27@gmail.com

Attiya Shahzadi³

Faculty of Sciences & Technology, Department of Microbiology, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.

Fatima Tariq⁴

Faculty of Sciences & Technology, Department of Microbiology, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.

Usman Wajid⁵

University Institute of Biochemistry and Biotechnology, Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Abbas Shahid⁶

Faculty of Sciences & Technology, Basic & Applied Chemistry, University of Central Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan.

Enterobacteriaceae, especially *Escherichia coli*, which produces extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) is a significant source of multidrug-resistant infection in the world. Antimicrobial resistance is becoming more and more common and is a major limitation to treatment choice as well as a major health concern to the population, particularly in developing nations such as Pakistan.

Methodology:

A total of 50 clinical samples (pus, urine, blood, and swabs) were collected from a tertiary care hospital in Lahore. Under CLSI guidelines, the bacterial isolates were cultured, Gram-stained, and tested by biochemical methods and subjected to antibiotic susceptibility testing by KirbyBauer method. Phenotypic screening of ESBL production was followed by a positive confirmation of the test using a double-disc synergy test. PCR was used to detect resistance genes (blaTEM, blaCTX-M, blaSHV). Phylogenetic analysis was performed on 16S rRNA gene amplification and confirmed the identity of bacteria using MEGA11.

Results:

They were all found to be Gram-negative bacilli, majorly *E. coli*. The resistance was high to aminopenicillins (88%) and cephalosporins (100%), but carbapenems were the most sensitive (imipenem 92%, meropenem 88%). Out of 25 ESBL-positive isolates, the most common gene was blaCTX-M (76%), then blaTEM (56%) and blaSHV (36%). PCR amplification was used to confirm gene-specific products and phylogenetic analysis showed that isolates were closely related to *E. coli* reference strains (OP762955.1 and OR349600.1).

Conclusion:

The research indicates a high rate of ESBL-producing *E. coli* with high resistance to the widely used antibiotics. The prevalence of blaCTX-M genes highlights the importance of the resistance in the dissemination process. An effective surveillance system, molecular monitoring and tough antimicrobial stewardship measures must be implemented to contain these resistant pathogens and enhance the clinical outcomes.

Background:

1. INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms are a major cause of disease and they were unable to be treated until the first development of Penicillin; a breakthrough in the medical history. This remarkable era glimpsed the discoveries of many antibiotics which seemed to be promising about treatment of diseases worldwide. But as the time elapsed the microbes adapted and demonstrated resistance to some drugs adding to the complications. In 2019, Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) alone; costed approx. 4.95 million lives globally and since then it is emerging as a serious public health threat. Moreover, it is expected that by 2050, death toll will rise to 10 million globally (Murray *et al.*, 2022).

Enterobacteriaceae is a large family of bacteria; primarily gram negative that normally inhabit intestinal flora and given the chance, they transmit quickly between humans. The common modes of transmission are contaminated food or water, hand carriage, and environmental sources. They are of high clinical significance and wide range of diagnostic cultures contains *E. coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., and *Enterobacter* spp. *E. coli* is rod shaped, coli form bacterium. It is normally found in the lower part of intestine of warm-blooded organisms. It can cause the urinary tract infection and the antibiotics that use for the treatment are Ampicillin, trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole (Shahid *et al.*, 2022). Since, the most frequent agents responsible for nosocomial and community acquired infections are associated with *Enterobacteriaceae* family, henceforth they hold a special significance whenever antibiotic resistance is mentioned (Van Duin & Paterson, 2016). The most common infection caused by these bacteria is UTI, and the emerging multidrug resistant (MDR) bacteria poses a serious threat as it makes it challenging to treat these infections using antimicrobial therapy. Infections caused by MDR *Enterobacteriaceae* results in severe health consequences, higher death toll and exhaustion of healthcare resources.

β -Lactam antibiotics are categorized into several classes which includes Penicillin, monobactams, Cephalosporins and Carbapenemes. The ideal medications for the treatment of infections caused by *Enterobacteriaceae* falls belongs to this category. However, last few decades marked significant rise in worldwide cases of the upsurge in resistance to this class of antibacterial (Kanamori *et al.*, 2011).

As the time passed; the bacteria belonging to this family have advanced their coping mechanisms to everchanging environment and they have developed resistance to antimicrobial agents which confers them with intrinsic capability to survive and reproduce, while repulsing the normal efficacy of antibacterial agent and rendering it resistant even to the last line Carbapenemes antibiotic. Hence, complicating the treatment of infections (O'Malley, 2020). In a normal setting, the passing time results in enhanced resistance conferred by the mutations and this enhanced rate is further amplified by improper use of antibiotic as it puts pressure on bacteria for natural selection (survival of the fittest). There are multiple reasons of the surge and transmission of antimicrobial resistance i-e; improper and excessive use of antibiotics; travelling and tourism, over-crowded spaces; improper personal hygiene etc.

These gram-negative bacteria produce enzymes that impart the resistance against beta lactam antibiotics. These enzymes cause hydrolysis of the amide bond present in β -lactam ring of the antibiotic including those with wider range of spectrum such as third and fourth generation of antibiotics (cephalosporin, ceftriaxone, and cefpirome), generally referred to as ESBLs and they are and now emerging and conferring resistant even against the last-line antibiotic, Carbapenemes (Silva-Sanchez *et al.*, 2011). These enzymes are called extended spectrum β Lactamases and they are reported to be highly frequent in the *Enterobacteriaceae* e and responsible for conferring resistance against β Lactam antibiotics and they are now a serious global health problem. (Bradford, 2001). The earliest ESBLs that were detected in the 1980s, that were formed as a consequence of genomic mutations in variants that were primarily non-ESBLs (Drawz & Bonomo, 2010). The earliest ESBLs belonged to the TEM and SHV families of enzymes, encoded by *blaSHV* and *blaTEM* types of ESBL genes. Hence, making them the commonest ESBL genotypes found in the strains of *Enterobacteriaceae* till 2000 (Thenmozhi *et al.*, 2014). These are named on the basis of sulfhydryl variable (SHV) enzymes and temoneira (TEM). Among these earliest detected ESBLs; TEM ESBL has quite vanished as suggested by the data but, SHV ESBLs are still

frequently reported and are regarded among the prevalent ESBLs globally. In the subsequent years, more families of enzymes demonstrating distinct ESBL phenotype was reported (Livermore, 2012).

Recent studies provided data suggesting that the variants with CTX-M family is more prevalent around the world encoded by *bla*CTX-M type genes (named after cefotaximase β -lactamases). And among CTX-M family, the most frequently detected enzyme in ESBL studies is CTX-M-15 encoded by *bla*CTX-M-15 genes, prevalent in the infectious strains of *Enterobacteriaceae* (Jacoby, 2009). CTX-M family resembles the family of SHV ESBLs. Moreover, studies have reported many other families of beta lactamases constituting of members with ESBL enzymes only, such as GES, VEB, BEL families belonging to Ambler class A. On the contrary, few members of some classes also contain ESBL enzymes along with others such as derivate of OXA-2 and OXA-10 belonging to Ambler class D.

The ESBL enzymes are encoded by β -lactamase (*bla*) genes that belong to plasmids (plasmid-encoded AmpC (pAmpC) β -lactamases) as well as on chromosomes. Most genes subtypes encoding for β -Lactamase are mainly associated with mobile genetic elements or MGEs which can be a plasmid, insertion sequence (ISs), integrons, or transposons. The genes encoding for ESBL enzymes are mainly present on the plasmid and mostly widespread in the *Enterobacteriaceae* family (Poole, 2004). The major reason behind the rapid spread of these genes between different bacterial species is due to fact that they are located on plasmids that facilitates the unfathomable spread of resistance among bacteria via horizontal gene transfer. The studies demonstrated that mobile genetic elements (MGEs) were involved in horizontal transfer of resistance genes between natural commensals and invading microbes in living organisms. *E. coli* have the potential to contribute in the spread of antibiotic resistance since it is a major commensal of humans which also persists within the environment, and some strains are also pathogenic (Stokes & Gillings, 2011). Among *Enterobacteriaceae* *E. coli* and *K. pneumonia* are important Extended-spectrum β -lactamase-generating antibiotic resistant organisms causing infections in human and they are responsible for urinary tract infections, septic infections including meningitis, endocarditis, and severe intra-abdominal infections throughout the world (Pitout, 2012). Humans are essentially sterile at birth, and as they interact with microbes, they create a microbiota and strengthen their immune systems at the same time (Shahid et al., 2023)

The unregulated use of antibiotics, inadequate hygiene measures in healthcare facilities, and the absence of effective monitoring contribute to the emergence and dissemination of ESBLs (Yusuf et al., 2013). Additional factors exacerbating the dissemination of ESBLs in third World nations are rooted to widespread auto medication and recommendation of antimicrobials without proper oversight, suboptimal hygiene standards, even within hospital settings, and insufficient infection control practices. These conditions create a conducive environment for the proliferation of ESBLs, posing a significant threat to public health (Oli et al., 2015).

Detection of ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* has been done using rapid detection techniques including ESBL HiCrome agar, ESBL E-test strips, and combined disk diffusion and these techniques implied similar potency for detection purpose. Several phenotypic tests such as isoelectric focusing can also be beneficial in identification of the presence of ESBL in the bacterial species but the processes have deemed to be more conventional as they are unable to distinguish properly between several subtypes of ESBLs. Studies suggest that molecular methods can be significant in order to detect the ESBL-producing genes in bacteria based upon the pattern of their sensitivity and providing important knowledge on the epidemiology of these bacteria which in turn aids to recommend the apt medications for the cure of infections within a clinical setting.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Enterobacteriaceae are significant hospital and community pathogens, and antimicrobial resistance has increased dramatically during the last 20 years as a result of antibiotics overuse and horizontal gene

transfer. This has given rise to multidrug-resistant (MDR) strains, which have greatly restricted treatment to counter and has resulted in increased risks to global health.

Enterobacteriaceae that produce extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL) are a dangerous group of MDR organisms, notably *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Such organisms usually carry resistance genes including blaCTX-M, blaTEM and blaSHV, usually co-existing in the same isolate. The spread of ESBLs across the world is geographically uneven, with high rates being reported in Pakistan and other developing countries, making it necessary to conduct constant monitoring.

Traditionally, ESBLs have undergone mutational changes in β -lactamase genes, which have allowed resistance to wide spectrum β -lactam antibiotics, including third generation cephalosporins. BlaCTX-M is the most prevalent of these worldwide, as well as blaTEM and blaSHV, which often cooccur and add to increased phenotypes of resistance.

The epidemiology of ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* underlines the presence of these bacteria in serious infections like bacteremia, urinary tract infections, and wound infections especially in the medical facilities. The prevalence rates are highly diverse (around 17-58 percent), and the risk factors are prior antibiotic use, hospitalization, and immunocompromised conditions. The COVID-19 pandemic has also impacted the trends of infections, yet its effect is not well understood.

Enterobacteriaceae resistance is mediated in several ways, including β -lactamase production, efflux pumps, target site modification, plasmid-mediated gene transfer, and biofilm formation. All these mechanisms improve bacterial survival and also add to multidrug resistance.

ESBL production is mainly caused by the genes blaTEM, blaSHV, and blaCTX-M, which are frequently found on mobile genetic elements, including plasmids, which allow the rapid horizontal spread of bacteria populations. This increases the proliferation of resistance in clinical and environmental environments.

The spread of ESBL-producing organisms has been facilitated by both horizontal gene transfer and clonal dissemination and is favoured by the environmental conditions, including the use of antibiotics in agriculture, wastewater pollution, and international travel. Such routes help to propagate resistant strains.

Enterobacteriaceae that produce ESBL are clinically linked with wound, urinary tract, blood, and respiratory infection. Surgical and burn wounds infections have been reported to be highly prevalent with predominant pathogens being *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. The emergence of carbapenem-resistant strains further complicates treatment strategies.

The environment reservoirs such as wastewater, vegetables, livestock, and poultry are also highly involved in transmission. Such sources enable the transmission of resistant bacteria to human populations and this is a serious issue in the context of the social health.

In order to overcome this increased threat, there is need to implement effective infection control measures. These are antimicrobial stewardship programs, surveillance programs, rigorous hygiene, isolation of patients, and intervention on a policy level. Enhancement of these mechanisms is vital to curb the ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* and maintain the effectiveness of the current antibiotics.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All chemicals used in this study were obtained from FDA-approved sources.

a. Sample Collection and Processing:

A total of 50 clinical samples (pus, urine, blood, and swabs) were collected from a tertiary care hospital in Lahore and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory, University of Central Punjab. Samples were cultured on MacConkey agar, nutrient agar, and CLED agar (for urine samples) and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Colony morphology and growth characteristics were recorded.

b. Isolation and Identification:

Bacterial isolates were identified using Gram staining and standard biochemical tests, including catalase,

oxidase, citrate, urease, triple sugar iron (TSI), and indole tests, following Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology.

c. Antibiotic Susceptibility Testing:

Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined using the Kirby–Bauer disc diffusion method on Mueller–Hinton agar. Bacterial suspensions were standardized to 0.5 McFarland, inoculated on plates, and incubated at 37°C for 18–24 hours. Zones of inhibition were measured according to CLSI guidelines. Antibiotics tested included ampicillin, gentamicin, amikacin, imipenem, meropenem, ceftriaxone, cefepime, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, doxycycline, and amoxicillin.

d. Screening and Confirmation of ESBL Production:

Initial screening for ESBL production was performed using the disc diffusion method. Confirmation was carried out using the double-disc synergy test (DDST) with third-generation cephalosporins and amoxicillin/clavulanic acid. An increase of ≥ 5 mm in inhibition zone was considered positive for ESBL production.

e. DNA Extraction and Molecular Analysis:

Genomic DNA was extracted using the GeneJET DNA extraction kit (Thermo Scientific) following the manufacturer's protocol. Extracted DNA was stored at -20°C for further analysis.

f. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR):

PCR was performed for detection of ESBL genes (blaTEM, blaCTX-M, and blaSHV). Each reaction mixture contained master mix, primers, nuclease-free water, and template DNA. Amplification conditions included initial denaturation at 94°C, followed by cycles of denaturation, annealing, extension, and final extension.

g. Gel Electrophoresis:

PCR products were analyzed using agarose gel electrophoresis (1–1.5%) prepared in TBE/TAE buffer with ethidium bromide. DNA bands were visualized under UV illumination using a gel documentation system.

h. Preservation of Isolates:

Bacterial isolates were preserved in glycerol stocks (15% glycerol) and stored at -20°C for future use

4. RESULTS

4.1. Identification of the Isolates

MacConkey agar and Nutrient Agar were used for culturing of the samples. The samples were labeled as A1 to A25. Bacterial isolates showed lactose fermenting pink mucoid colonies on MacConkey agar. Whereas, white mucoid colonies were obtained on Nutrient agar.

Figure 1: (A) Growth on MacConkey agar (B) Growth on Nutrient agar

4.2. Gram staining

The gram staining showed gram-negative bacilli on microscopic slides.

Figure 2: Gram -ve rod-shape bacteria observed in 100X oil immersion lens

4.3. Biochemical Testing

The identification of bacterial Isolates was done by various biochemical test include TSI, oxidase, cat bacteriology.

4.3.1. Catalase test

Active bubbling (due to production of oxygen gas), when organism immersed with H_2O_2 observed during catalase test. The bubble formation indicates positive test results.

4.3.2. Oxidase test

Color changes to dark purple within 5 – 10 seconds after adding oxidase reagent indicates oxidase positive whereas oxidase test results were observed as oxidase negative as the bacterial strains showed no color change to dark purple when reagent is added.

4.3.3. Citrate test

Color turns from green to blue indicate positive citrate test whereas if the color of the medium (strains) remains green the citrate test is negative.

4.3.4. Urease test

Used for the identification of the microorganisms those can breakdown urea to NH_3 and CO_2 . Pink color indicates a positive urine test result while on the other hand if the color of medium remains orange it indicates negative urease test.

4.3.5. TSI test

Yellow butt, yellow slant with no gas or H_2S and gas production indicate positive TSI.

4.3.6. Indole test

Test used for the differentiation of test organisms from other members of *Enterobacteriaceae*. Yellow ring on the top indicates positive Indole test.

4.4. Antibiotic sensitivity Testing (AST)

After confirmation of *E. coli* strain Antibiotic sensitivity test is performed on isolates according to CLSI guideline. The diameter of zone of inhibition in mm was measured to determine antibiotic sensitivity. The antibiotics resistance against different classes is given in table 1 bellow.

Table 1: Antibiotic Sensitivity profile of Each Antibiotic

Group of Antibiotics	Name of antibiotic	Resistant (%)	Sensitive (%)
Aminoglycosides	Gentamycin	28	72
	Amikacin	24	76
Aminopenicilline	Amoxillin/Clavulanic acid	84	16
	Ampicillin	88	12
	Piperacillin / Tazobactam	60	40
Anti-Folates	Co-trimoxazole	52	48
Carbapenemes	Meropenem	12	88
	Imipenem	8	92
Cephalosporins	Cefipime	100	0
	Ceftriaxone	100	0
Fluroquinolones	Levofloxacin	48	52
	Ciprofloxacin	64	36
Tetracycline	Doxycycline	36	64
Misc Agents	Fosfomycin	8	92
	Nitrofurantoin	16	84

Graph 1: Antibiotic Sensitivity pattern of different groups of antibiotics

Graph 2: Antibiotic Sensitivity profile of each antibiotic

4.5. Confirmation of ESBL *E. coli*

Out of 25 ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates tested, the numbers of resistant samples for each antibiotic were:

Figure 3: Antibiotic Susceptibility testing

4.6. DNA Extraction of ESBL *E. coli* strains.

All the positive ESBL strains (25) were selected for DNA extraction. DNA was extracted by using ThermoScientific GeneJET DNA purification kit™ method. DNA bands were observed on 1% agarose gel. The 1kb ladder was run with the samples.

Figure 4: Bacterial DNA (1-24) on 1% agarose gel, 1Kb ladder was loaded with samples

4.7. Molecular identification of bacterial isolates by 16Sr RNA

16Sr RNA was carried to amplify the conserved gene using the universal primers of 27F and 1492R. The PCR amplicon size of 1500 bp was obtained on 2% agarose gel. The ladder of 1kb was run with samples.

Figure 5: PCR amplification of bacterial 16S rRNA gene

The evolutionary history the bacterial strains that were isolated was determined by MEGA 11 software. Both of the isolated strains were mostly similar to *E. coli*. The strain 1 was highly similar to accession number OP762955.1. Whereas, the strain2 was highly similar to accession number OR349600.

Figure 6: Neighbour-joining phylogenetic tree of strain 1 based on 16S rRNA sequences showing close similarity to *E. coli* (accession OP762955.1) with bootstrap support (1000 replicates).

Figure 7: Neighbour-joining phylogenetic tree of strain 2 based on 16S rRNA sequences showing close similarity to *E. coli* (accession OR349600.1) constructed using MEGA11 with bootstrap analysis (1000 replicates).

The evolutionary history of strain 2 was inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method. The optimal tree is shown. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (1000 replicates) are shown next to the branches. The tree is drawn to scale, with branch lengths in the same units as those of the evolutionary distances used to infer the phylogenetic tree. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Maximum Composite Likelihood method and are in the units of the number of base substitutions per site. This analysis involved 12 nucleotide sequences. All ambiguous positions were removed for each sequence pair (pairwise deletion option). There were a total of 1286 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11.

4.8. Genotypic analysis of ESBL *E. coli* resistant genes.

The *bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{TEM}* and *bla_{SHV}* genes were detected to confirm the resistance of ESBL *E. coli* using real time PCR. Primers for the following genes are given below.

Table 2: Primers, product size and Temp for the genes caused antibiotic resistance in ESBL *E. coli*

Primers	Sequence (5'-3')	Product size (bp)	Annealing Temp
bla_{TEM}	Forward- GAGACAATAACCCTGGTAAAT	459	54.9
	Reverse- AGAAGTAAGTTGGCAGCAGTG		
bla_{CTX-M}	Forward- TTTGCATGTGCAGTACCAGTAA	544	55
	Reverse- CGATATCGTTGGTGGTGCCATA		
bla_{SHV}	Forward- TCGTTATGCGTTATATTCGCC	868	56
	Reverse- -GGTTAGCGTTGCCAGTGCT		

4.9. Amplification of bla_{TEM} gene

Total of 25 samples that were positive for ESBL subjected to molecular identification. After PCR amplification at 54.9°C the product was loaded in 2% agarose Gel for visualization and quantification of bands against 100bp ladder. The amplicon size of bla_{TEM} gene was 459bp. Out of 25 isolates 14 were found positive for bla_{TEM} gene.

Figure 8: Bands of bla_{TEM} product size 459bp

4.10. Amplification of bla_{CTX-M} gene

Figure 9: Bands of bla_{CTX-M} Product size 544bp

The bla_{CTX-M} gene was also amplified to confirm the resistance against this class of antibiotics. After PCR amplification at 55°C the bands of 100bp were visualized. Out of 25 isolates 19 were found positive for bla_{CTX-M} gene.

4.11. Amplification of bla_{SHV} gene

The bla_{SHV} gene was also amplified to confirm the resistance against this class of antibiotics. After PCR amplification at 56°C the bands of 100bp were visualized. Out of 25 isolates 9 were found positive for bla_{SHV} gene.

Figure 10: Bands of bla_{SHV} product size 868bp

Discussion

Enterobacteriaceae family is of high clinical significance since, the most frequent agents responsible for nosocomial and community acquired infections are associated with it, henceforth they hold a special significance whenever antibiotic resistance is mentioned (Van Duin & Paterson, 2016). In this study the ESBL genes and their resistance profiles have been determined in organisms, the typical organisms identified include *E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Lynch III et al., 2021).

A study suggested that 15% urine samples showed significant growth of *E. coli* while 7% pus and sputum samples showed significant growth of *E. coli*. 96.10% of *E. coli* isolates from urine, were MDR. Among *E. coli* MDR isolates 70.27% were ESBL producers. All the isolates of *E. coli* from pus and sputum were

MDR which were resistant to tested third generation cephalosporins (Kumar, 2014).

In the present study, the resistance patterns of ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* were studied revealed significant resistance patterns among the isolates, particularly against Aminopenicillin (77%) and Cephalosporins (100%). This high resistance aligns with global trends, highlighting the widespread challenge of managing infections caused by ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* (Humphries et al., 2021).

The sensitivity against each antibiotic was as follows Aminoglycosides (74%), Antifolates (48%), Carbapenem (90%), Fluoroquinolones (44%), Tetracycline (64%) and miscellaneous agents (88%). The resistance pattern against each of the individual antibiotics was as follows Gentamycin (72%), Amikacin (76%), Amoxicillin (16%), Ampicillin (12%), Piperacillin (40%), Cotrimoxazole (48%), meropenem (88%), Imipenem (92%), Cefepime (0%), Ceftriaxone (0%), Levofloxacin (52%), Ciprofloxacin (36%), Doxycycline (64%), Fosfomycin (92%), Nitrofurantoin (84%).

The similar study was conducted in Sudan (Ibrahim, 2023) which reported the resistance level of amoxicillin (97.7%), tetracycline (77.1%), ceftriaxone (64%), ciprofloxacin (58.4%), amoxicillin-clavulanate (50.4%), ceftazidime, gentamicin (35%) each, nitrofurantoin (22.4%), and amikacin (1.9%). urine 93 (21.9%), vaginal swab 175 (41.4%) and urethral swab cultures 155 (36.6%). These results were significantly lower than another study conducted in Buea Health District, Cameroon in which all the isolates showed significantly high resistance rates to amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (67.6%), but most isolates were relatively more susceptible to nitrofurantoin (82.6%) (Amin et al., 2018).

According to another retrospective study in China, the *Enterobacteriaceae* showed resistance to Carbapenems, such as meropenem and imipenem were 12.34% and 10.63% respectively (Wu et al., 2023) and it aligns well with results of this research indicating their continued efficacy against these resistant strains. However, the emergence of carbapenem resistance remains a critical concern, as it limits treatment options and necessitates the development of new therapeutic strategies (Bush & Bradford, 2020). The relatively lower resistance rates observed for Fosfomycin and nitrofurantoin (8% and 16%, respectively) suggest these agents could be viable alternatives for dealing with infections caused by ESBL-producing *E. coli* (Paul et al., 2022).

The molecular findings of a study (Pishtiwan, 2019) showed that out of the collected strains of ESBL-producing *E. coli*, had 81% bla_{TEM}, 16.2% bla_{SHV}, and 32.4% bla_{CTX-M} genes. Whereas, in the current study the molecular analysis identified the bla_{CTX-M}, bla_{SHV} and bla_{TEM} genes in the isolates, with the bla_{TEM} along with bla_{CTX-M} detected in 14 and 19 out of 25 ESBL-producing isolates, respectively. This finding contradicts the previous studies as bla_{CTX-M} is predominant in isolates while past studies reported bla_{TEM} to be highly prevalent. This underscores the predominant role of these genes in conferring ESBL resistance and highlights the need for continuous monitoring and molecular characterization to track the emergence and spread of these resistance genes.

Conclusion

This research was focused on elucidating the incidence rate and genetic properties of ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolated from clinical specimens in Lahore, Pakistan. The antibiotic sensitivity testing (AST), performed according to guidelines by CLSI, revealed significant resistance patterns among the isolates, particularly against Aminopenicilline and Cephalosporins, with 88% and 100% resistance, respectively. Carbapenemes, such as Meropenem and Imipenem, exhibited the lowest resistance rates (12% and 8%, respectively), highlighting their continued efficacy against these resistant strains (Humphries et al., 2021). Molecular analysis using real-time PCR identified the key ESBL resistance genes bla_{TEM}, bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{SHV} and genes in the isolates, these were detected in 14, 19 and 9 out of 25 ESBL-producing isolates, respectively. This underscores the predominant role of these genes in conferring resistance and highlights the urgent need for targeted antibiotic stewardship strategies to combat this issue (Hamwi & Salem-Sokhn, 2023). Future research should focus on developing rapid diagnostic tools, exploring novel therapeutic

approaches, and strengthening antibiotic stewardship programs. Additionally, there is a need for ongoing surveillance and molecular characterization of antibiotic-resistant pathogens to continue building on the knowledge base established by this study (Bush & Bradford, 2020).

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